

WP3 – Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Certification and Branding of Agroforestry Products

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	3: Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services
Deliverable	Deliverable 3.6: Certification and branding of agroforestry products
Date of report	28 June 2024
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DigitAF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N°101059794. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Research Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive summary

The purpose of this report, produced by the DigitAF project, is to initiate the development of best practice guidelines on how certification and branding can improve the value and marketability of agroforestry products.

The introduction explains the context of the report within the wider DigitAF project that is seeking to promote agroforestry through the provision and promotion of digital tools pertinent to policy makers, producers, or stakeholders in agroforestry value chains. The second section of the report emphasizes the foundational role of government regulation in providing minimum standards for agroforestry products, and indeed, all food products, particularly in relation to food safety and environmental impact. Certification and branding seek to build on these minimum standards, ideally with the principal attributes of agroforestry production processes aligning with the principal concerns of consumers. As noted elsewhere, few agroforestry products are competitive with non-agroforestry products based on price alone. However, agroforestry practices can enhance biodiversity, animal welfare, carbon sequestration, and rural economies, which are also of concern to many people. Certification and branding are established ways of conveying positive attributes to consumers and they can also create benefits for producers and retailers in terms of improved client relationships and access to markets. However, certification and branding also create additional costs.

Certification systems typically include an organisation that promotes the system and an independent auditor, and the certification process has to manage trade-offs between certification costs, robustness, and uptake. Some agroforestry products, such as high value meat from the dehesa in Spain, are already being certified through blockchain traceability schemes, and other specialist products such as nut oils, are part of the European Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) scheme. In the context of climate change, certified “carbon-neutral” agricultural products which typically involve the use of trees on farms are starting to appear in supermarkets, and it is anticipated that the number of such products will increase. There are also certification schemes, often promoted by conservation charities, that certify the biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, such as high stem orchards in Switzerland. In each of these examples, the certification system encompasses agroforestry because it supports a broader objective. However, recently there have been attempts, with government financial support, to develop a bespoke agroforestry label, most notably the Agro Farm Forestry label in the Netherlands which places a substantial emphasis on social engagement. It is anticipated that the development of such initiatives is likely to need continued government support.

Branding, unlike certification, does not require independent auditing, and is also a possible means of promoting agroforestry products. Individual organisations, or groups of individuals, can brand and market their own products and can capitalise on awards such as “best agroforestry product”. Individual processors and supermarkets may also support agroforestry through their own tree-related branding schemes. Many of the above points are summarized in a concluding section. This initial report will be developed over the next two years into a further report (Deliverable 3.7) in June 2026 which will provide guidelines for farmers and actors in the value chain on how to build agroforestry businesses supported by new certification and branding approaches.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 to June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims to support high-quality implementation of agroforestry in Europe to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. The project uses a participatory research approach to engage with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholders and other research to facilitate the implementation of innovations. An overall objective of the project is to provide three groups of stakeholders with digital tools that address their needs and expectation. The three groups are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the sequestered carbon and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

This deliverable (D3.6) forms part of work-package 3 in the DigitAF project which deals with the verification and accounting of the benefits of agroforestry practices for stakeholders in the value chain. A recent analysis of value added chains networks associated with agroforestry highlighted that agroforestry products are unlikely to compete in the market place on the basis of price alone (Burgess et al., 2024). Instead, most agroforestry systems are likely to depend on a process of “adding value” to agroforestry products and services through certification and branding (EIP-AGRI, 2017). A further output (Deliverable 3.7) will be produced in June 2026 comprising guidelines for farmers and actors in the value chain to design business plans building on new certification and branding approaches.

1.2 Aim, objectives and structure

In view of the above, the aim of this report is to describe the current status of certification and branding for agroforestry products and services. This report has two objectives:

- To outline the potential role of government regulation, consumer choice, certification, and branding to increase the standards of food production.
- To highlight case studies where certification and branding can promote agroforestry products and services.

The content of the report has drawn on the experience of participants within the DigitAF project. Section two starts with the role of government and consumers. Section three focuses on certification. The fourth section focuses on branding, and there is a final concluding section.

2. The role of government and consumers

2.1 Regulation

Although this report is about certification and branding, it is still important to emphasise the role of government in establishing regulations concerning basic standards of food and fibre products. In 2002, the European Union adopted the General Food Law Regulation (European Commission, 2002). This regulation provides general principles, requirements and procedures related to **food and feed safety**. The regulation also set up the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to provide independent scientific advice and support.

Meuwissen et al. (2003), focused on the meat sector, argued that food safety and hygiene were governed by the development of i) food safety and hygiene systems, ii) traceability systems, and iii) certification, although there is some overlap (Figure 1). Angus et al. (2023) argue that much of the recent regulation of food has placed much of the legal responsibility for food safety on the private sector. In turn this has forced European retailers to develop their own certification standards (Figure 1). For example in 1997, European retailers and supply chain stakeholders formed the European Retailers' Protocol for Good Agricultural Practice (EurepGAP) to create a uniform set of standards for all retailers (Campbell, 2005). Campbell (2005) argues that EurepGAP is a "new mode of authority outside the conventional democratic nation state". As the importance of certification has increased over time and moved to a global stage, EUREP-GAP was renamed as GLOBALG.A.P in 2007 (GLOBALG.A.P., 2024).

Figure 1. The use of certification exists alongside regulatory standards which are often set at country level (Meuwissen et al., 2003)

2.2 Consumer choice

Alongside governments, consumers also determine what goods are produced and often how they are produced through their effect on the market. For example, a recent survey in the UK highlighted the priority placed by many consumers on animal welfare (Figure 2). Whilst government regulation may provide minimum standards for animal welfare, many consumers would like to purchase products where the standard of animal welfare or the means of production are above those minimum levels. In these situations, producers, aware of these customer demands, may work with stakeholder groups and certifiers to "co-create" certification systems or brands (Starr and Brodie, 2016). However, such choices are often individually made. For example, a consumer with strong environmental concerns can derive positive "value" from a certified organic product, but another consumer may consider the product to be costly and irrelevant.

Figure 2. Customers perceptions of what UK farmers should prioritise. Consumers were asked to prioritise up to two areas (n = 3564) (YouGov 2021)

3. Certification

3.1 Attributes of certification

In general, farm or farm product “certification” schemes expand on the standard surveillance undertaken by national authorities to maintain regulatory standards related to food safety and animal welfare. Although most certification schemes are voluntary, they typically include formal certification processes.

Starr and Brodie (2016) used the term certification to describe “an explicit formal process for adding credible extrinsic information about the attributes of a product or service.” They also indicated that the process includes verbal or symbolic communication of the adherence to those standards. Lozej and Visković (2022) defined certification as a process by which “an independent organisation verifies that a product, process, or service meets certain standards”. Meuwissen et al. (2003) also describe certification as “the (voluntary) assessment and approval by a (accredited) party on a (accredited) standard”. Hence, certification schemes are typically designed to provide credibility to claims of the attributes of a product or the process of production through the use of a third party (Starr and Brodie, 2016; Chever et al., 2022). Examples of types of certification scheme are outlined in Table 1. Agroforestry practices can support many of the objectives of these certification schemes.

Table 1. Example types of certification schemes adapted from Chever et al. (2022)

Scheme	Description
1 Good agricultural practices	Schemes focusing on environmentally friendly methods of production
2 Animal welfare and health	Focus on animal welfare and health
3 Origin/quality of the final products	Schemes guaranteeing a specific origin and/or attributes on the final product
4 Organic+	Based on organic standards, with some additional rules
5 Climate	Specific focus on climate-related issues
6 Multi-purpose	Focus on a combination of issues, for instance good agricultural practices and quality management
7 Traceability/safety	Schemes committing to provide high transparency on the origin and quality management of products all along the supply chain
8 Non-genetically modified	Main guarantee is the absence of genetically modified organisms
9 Fairtrade	Focus on social and ethical trade commitments

Another feature of certification is that it is typically used by more than one producer. For example, the law in the United States (Public Law 489, Lanham Act H.R. 1654, 1946) specifies that a certification mark “must attest to the presence or absence of particular attributes and be used by at least one other entity beyond the owner of the mark” (Starr and Brodie, 2016).

Certification schemes can operate either between businesses (B2B) or between businesses and consumers (B2C). The objective of many “business-to-business” certification schemes is to protect buyers from supplier practices that could be harmful to their customers and brand, for instance, keeping livestock in unsanitary conditions. As indicated previously, some of the farm assurance schemes have emerged as a private sector response to a series of European food safety concerns and regulatory responses in the 1990s, combined with the acceleration of globalisation from the 1994 round of talks on the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) (Anders et al., 2010).

Whereas the use of logos in “business-to-business” certification may be minimal, almost all “business-to-consumer” certification schemes use logos and branding to enable consumers to identify preferred products (Angus et al., 2010). Examples of ten certification logos used in the UK are shown in Figure 3. However, if the logo in itself is to be effective, then it is necessary both for consumers to recognise the logo and consider it important. This is not always the case, and even for the ten “common logos used on food products of the UK”, only six were recognised by over half of consumers in a recent UK survey (Figure 4). The high ranking of the British Lion quality mark, used on British eggs, may be partly because it is also a traceability system where a number printed on each egg highlights the country of origin, farming method, best before dates, and farm ID of each egg (Egginfo, 2023).

Figure 3. Ten common logos used on food products in the United Kingdom

Figure 4. Recognition of ten food certification logos in the United Kingdom, and the proportion of those who felt the logo was very or quite important (n = 3564) (YouGov, 2011)

Another attribute of certification is that it incurs costs and these are typically borne by the supplier. In many cases, the argument is that this is financially worthwhile because the farmer will achieve a higher price, but in some cases, certification may be needed just to secure a contract or the capacity to trade in a market. There are also cost implications for certifiers whose activities also need to be financially viable. Hence, certifiers need to balance the trade-off between the cost of certification and the robustness of the certification (Angus et al., 2010). But even with the most robust scheme, there may be errors or limitations due to, for example, human error (Meuwissen et al., 2003). These challenges mean that the certification ecosystem can become quite complicated. For example, an accreditation ecosystem can include the firms seeking accreditation, the owners of the standard, accreditation agencies, and third party certifiers. However, third-party certification bodies can provide an “independent and credible signal” about differentiating qualities of products (Anders et al. 2010).

3.2 International certification schemes

3.2.1 GLOBALG.A.P.

There are a number of international certification schemes. GLOBALG.A.P. reports that it is one of the “most widely recognized certification systems in the global trade of farmed products” (GLOBALG.A.P., 2023). The legal entity for the GLOBALG.A.P. secretariat is FoodPLUS GmbH in Germany. As an international body, GLOBALG.A.P. has established memorandums of understanding with national accreditation bodies (Figure 5). The systems that it manages include aquaculture, arable crops, flowers and ornamentals, fruit and vegetables, hops, and plant propagation material.

Figure 5. The GLOBALG.A.P. system comprises memorandums of understanding with national accreditation bodies which can accredit certification bodies using the ISO/IEC 17-65 framework (GLOBALG.A.P., 2023b)

Within the European Union and the UK, GLOBALG.A.P. is reported to set the minimum requirement for Integrated Farm Assurance (IPA) for most imported fresh fruit and vegetables (CBI, 2022). The requirements potentially cover six impact areas: i) food safety, ii) environmental sustainability, iii) workers’ well-being, iv) animal welfare, v) supply chain traceability, and vi) capacity building (GLOBALG.A.P., 2023).

Within the GLOBALG.A.P. ecosystem, **accreditation bodies** ensure high quality standards and integrity at a national level. Each accreditation body (AB) is required to sign a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with FoodPLUS GmbH, be a member of the International Accreditation Forum (IAF), and be a signatory of the IFA’s Multilateral Recognition Arrangement (MLA) for product certification. The IAF identifies “Accreditation Bodies” that have joined the MLA (IAF, 2024). In most countries there is only one accreditation body within the GLOBALG.A.P. system (Table 2).

However, within a country, there may be more than one approved **certification board**. In some countries such as the UK, there may be only one certification board, but in some countries such as Italy and Spain, there are more than 10 certification boards (Table 2).

Table 2. Accreditation bodies and certification boards approved by GLOBALG.A.P in selected European countries for combinable crops (GLOBALG.A.P., 2023b)

Country	Accreditation body	Approved certification board
France	Comite Francais d'Accreditation - COFRAC	Bureau Veritas Certification France, CERTIPAQ, CERTIS, Ecocert Environnement SAS, Qualisud
Germany	Deutsche Akkreditierungsstelle GmbH - DAkkS	ABCERT AG, ACG Agrar-Control GmbH, CERES, LKSmbH, QAL GmbH, SGS Germany GmbH, SRS Certification GmbH
Italy	Sistema Nazionale Accreditamento - ACCREDIA	Agroqualita' SPA, Bioagricert srl, Bureau Veritas Italia SPA, CCPB SRL, Centro di Speirmentazione e Assistenza Agricola, Certiquality S.r.l. CODES SRL, CSI SPA, CSQA Certificazioni Srl, DNV Business Assurance Italy SRL, ICEA, RINA Services SPA, SGS Italia SPA, Suolo e Salute SRL
Spain	ENAC	4Plus Ingeieros y Arquitectos S.L., AB-Aucatel Organismo de Cerificacion S.L.U., Acerta Certicacion S.L., Agencia para la Certificacion de la Calidad y el Medio Ambiente, Agrocolor S.L., Applus, Bureau Veritas Iberia S.L., Certifood, ECCO Ingenieros SL, ITACA, Kiwa Espana SLU, Norma Agricola SL, SAI Global Certification Services Pty Ltd, Servicio de Certificacion CAAE, SGS ICS Iberica SA, Sohiscert SA, Sygma Certification SL
United Kingdom	United Kingdom Accreditation Service - UKAS	BSI Assurance Ltd

At a national level, certification boards can issue their own quality marks. For example, BSI Assurance Ltd in the UK issues a British Kite mark for Food Assurance. As part of the British Kite mark scheme, Morrisons which is a supermarket in the UK has established “carbon neutral” eggs (Figure 6). The assessment of net zero greenhouse gas emissions from farm to shelf is in part due to the establishment of trees in association with egg production – a form of agroforestry (Morrisons, 2024). Carbon neutral eggs are also being sold by Sainsburys supermarkets in the UK (Sainsburys, 2024).

Figure 6. Morrisons supermarket in the UK is retailing “carbon neutral” eggs as determined by the BSI Kite Mark (Morrisons, 2024)

A second example is CERTIS, an approved certifier in France, and the independent certifier of “Label Haie” certification system that promotes products such as wood from “bocage” hedgerows in France (Label Haie, 2024) (Figure 7). Label Haie indicates that it promotes rural development and the value of traditional landscapes and ecosystems. The cost of individual certification to a business manager is €350 per year, of which €100 goes to Label Haie and €250 goes to CERTIS.

Figure 7. Label Haie is a certification system that promotes products from “bocage” hedgerows in France (Label Haie, 2024)

Although GLOBALG.A.P. started an accreditation scheme for livestock in 2005, the Integrated Farm Assurance (IFA) standard for livestock was discontinued in June 2022 because it was not becoming an international standard (GLOBALG.A.P., 2023c). Instead the GLOBALG.A.P. website points to the Spanish Sustainable Beef Alliance called DEFHESA (DEFHESA, 2023). The details of the DEFHESA scheme are described in Case Study 1. In the context of the DigitAF project which focuses on digital tools, both the “de Dehesa” and “Iberchain” blockchain systems collect and process significant quantities of information whilst also ensuring its integrity, confidentiality, and transparency at specific points in the chain (Tranchina et al., 2023).

Case study 1. Development of a blockchain traceability system in Spain

In 2021, an association of extensive beef producers (UGAVAN), a co-operative of dehesa cattle farmers (Dehesa Grande), and a co-operative of Iberian livestock producers in Spain worked together with a feed supplier, a veterinary group, local government, an international programme, and three universities to develop the SOSTVAN Operational Group. An objective of the group was to develop a pilot “blockchain” traceability system using extensive beef production in Spain as a case study (Tranchina et al., 2023). The acronym SOSTVAN is derived from “Sostenibilidad de las Vacas Nodrizas” which means the sustainability of suckler cows (SOSTVAN, 2018). Much of the extensive beef in Spain is produced in the dehesa agroforestry system where beef cattle are reared in a parkland landscape of low-density oak trees. The pilot blockchain system included animal records, feed nutrition, animal welfare, slaughter stage, farm nature values, carbon footprint, transport, sales, and traceability (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The traceability system within the pilot SOSTVAN blockchain system (Tranchina et al., 2023), and the logos for “de Dehesa” and “Iberchain” certification (Defhesa, 2021; Iberchain Cartel, 2022)

The lessons learnt in the pilot SOSTVAN blockchain system have been taken up by two commercial systems.

The Spanish Sustainable Beef Alliance (DEFHESA) has created a digital system to trace, audit and certify extensive beef products produced on “sustainable grazing farms”. They have recently created the “de Dehesa” brand (Figure 8). The owners of the “de Dehesa” certification indicate that the label guarantees animal welfare, quality and sustainability, and that the standards audited and certified by GLOBALG.A.P..

The Iberchain certification scheme has been created to confirm the traceability of pig meat including the confirmation that it has been produced with pure native Iberian breeds fattened in free-range dehesas (Iberchain Cartel, 2022; Tranchina et al., 2023).

3.2.2 Programme for Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)

The Programme for Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC), created in 1999, describes itself as the world’s largest forest certification system with a particular focus on owners of smaller forests (PEFC, 2024). However, it was only in 2018 that PEFC agreed an international standard for trees outside forests, which could potentially address agroforestry systems (PEFC, 2018). Even so, there is still a need to implement such standards at a national level.

Between 2019 and 2023, the “NETwork per l’agroselvicultura in TOscaN” (NEWTON) Operation Group aimed to promote agroforestry practices in Tuscany in Italy as a means of improving socio-economic and environmental sustainability (EIP-AGRI, 2024). One of the objectives of NEWTON was to promote the value of agroforestry production through the development of an agroforestry certification system that addressed economic, environmental, and social issues.

As part of the project, PEFC Italy organized and conducted seven official online meetings involving 22 organizations representing the agroforestry sector in Italy, with 38 active participants, including researchers and project partner companies. The meetings focused on the requirements of PEFC International, examining these with forum experts, and also focused on national regulations, using the management systems of NEWTON project partner companies as case studies. As a result of studies completed at the Tenuta di Paganico farm, the guidelines and indicators of a PEFC sustainable management standard for agroforestry (PEFC ITA 1001-5) was developed and opened for consultation in 2023 (PEFC, 2023) (Figure 9). It is anticipated that the PEFC Italy scheme will offer economic benefits to actors in the agroforestry value chain, and potentially open new routes to market for agroforestry products.

Figure 9. Criteria and indicators for management certification of Italian sustainable agroforestry systems (PEFC, 2023)

3.3 European Union certification related to geography and quality

Within the European Union, an important source of certification relating to geographic origins are the protected designation of origin (PDO), protected geographical indication (PGI), and geographic indication (GI) labels (Figure 10). There is also a traditional speciality guarantee (TSG). Some agroforestry products, such as walnut oil from the Vaud district of Switzerland, are protected through the system (Case study 2). Such certification of authenticity is usually viewed positively by consumers and hence this certification leads to greater product value (Starr and Brodie, 2016). Such certification also minimises competition of other products from other locations.

Figure 10. The European Union protects some products linked to specific geographies and qualities (European Commission, 2024)

Case study 2. Walnut oil from the Vaud District of Switzerland

In French, a PDO designation is known as an AOP (Appellation d'Origine Protégé). Vaudoise walnut oil from Switzerland has been a recognised AOP product since 2020 (Swiss PDO-PGI Association, 2024). The oil is pressed using traditional methods from walnuts that must be grown in the Vaud district of Switzerland. There is evidence that walnut oil been produced in the area since the thirteenth century.

Figure 11. Vaudoise walnut oil has protected designation of origin (Origin Food, 2024)

3.4 Organic certification

Organic agriculture has been defined as “a production management system which promotes and enhances agroecosystem health including biodiversity, biological cycles, and soil biological activity” (FAO and WHO, 1999). However, a key feature of organic agriculture is also the avoidance of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides (FAO and WHO 1999). The definition of what is or what is not organic can be set at a national level. For example, in the UK, the Organic Products Regulations (UK Government 2009) specifies that UK growers, processors and importers who sell feed and food as “organic” need to be registered with one of six approved organisations (UK Government 2020) (Table 3). Although organic certification does not mean that a product has been produced using agroforestry, a substantial number of agroforestry systems have been developed on organic farms (Burgess et al., 2024).

Table 3. Example organic certification schemes in the UK

Scheme name	Managing organisation	Scheme coverage
Soil Association Organic	Soil Association	Based on retained Regulation (EC) No. 834/2007, (EC) No. 889/2008, (EC) No. 1235/2008 and Organic Products Regulation 2009
Organic Farmers and Growers	OF&G Organic	Based on Retained Regulation (EC) No. 834/2007, (EC) No. 889/2008, (EC) No. 1235/2008 and Organic Products Regulation 2009.
Organic Food Federation	Organic Food Federation	Based on council Regulation 834/2007 and 889/2008 which is the official definitive legal standard within the EU.
BDA Organic	Biodynamic UK Association	Aligns with the UK retained organic regulations (EC 834/2007 and EC 889/2008)

3.5 Other certification schemes

There are also other environmental certification schemes, beyond organic, that are pertinent to agroforestry products. Some of these schemes have been developed by conservation charities which seek to improve biodiversity by promoting biodiversity-friendly products. For example, in 2000, BirdLife Switzerland and Pro Natura worked together with others to create the “Hochstamm Suisse” or “High Stem Swiss” label (Figure 12). This label assures the consumer that the product comes from the fruit of standard-sized trees in Switzerland and that “processors have paid farming families a fair price” (Hochstamm Suisse, 2018). The products include fresh and frozen fruit, fruit drinks, yoghurts, spirits, vinegars, and oils.

Figure 12. The Hochstamm Suisse label in Switzerland covers products from high stem trees (Hochstamm Suisse, 2018)

In a similar way, “Fair to Nature” is a certification scheme managed by the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB) in the UK. The certification scheme focuses on biodiversity, and farmers receiving the certification must dedicate at least 10% of farmed land to habitats conducive to biodiversity and manage soils and inputs in an environmentally sensitive manner. The certification is applied at the farm level (Fair to Nature, 2023). Farmers participating in the scheme receive a “Fair to Nature Habitat Assessment” visit by an approved adviser every two years, and those with a supply contract will also be audited every two years. The audit covers 10 areas comprising documentation, conservation and habitats, soil management, carbon management, livestock management, pesticide management, fertilizer and manure management, water and pollution management, training, and legal and regulatory compliance (Fair to Nature, 2023).

The case study farm within the UK DigitAF Living Lab is Hope Farm which is managed by RSPB (Figure 13). The intention with the agroforestry system is to produce nut oil and apple juice and to sell the products through a network of RSPB shops using the “Fair to Nature” label.

Figure 13. The plan with a new silvoarable agroforestry system at Hope Farm in England is to produce apple juice and cobnut oil with the “Fair to Nature” label

3.6 Agroforestry certification

For most of Europe, there is no bespoke agroforestry certification. In Germany, Kopplin and Sänn (2020) examined the acceptability of an agroforestry “quality seal”. On the basis of feedback, the impact of agroforestry on animal welfare, biodiversity and sustainability was highlighted (Figure 14). The second part of the study was a quantitative study of 184 customers.

Figure 14. A proposed agroforestry label for use in Germany [Agroförstwirtschaft is German for agroforestry; “Nachhaltigkeit hat einen Namen” is translated “Sustainability has a name”) (Kopplin and Sänn, 2020)

More recently, an agroforestry certification scheme, including independent validation, has been developed in the Netherlands. The “Agro Farm Forestry” (AFF) label demonstrates an independent validation that agroforestry is being applied on a farm (Agro Farm Forestry Label, 2023) (Figure 15). The labelling process was created within an EU FarmLife project that ran from 2018 to 2024. Although the label applies to the farm, the promotional material indicates that the farmer can also put the label on products, but the label should not be used “for further links in the chain”. The label is awarded according to nine criteria including issues such as soil improvement, biodiversity, carbon and water management, but also social engagement (Table 4). The certification is managed by the Forestry Service Group (Forestry Service Group, 2022). Organisations that have received the certification have to pay a fee of €350 and they are then listed on the Agro Farm Forestry webpage (Agro Farm Forestry Label, 2023).

Figure 15. The Agro Farm Forestry Label (Agro Farm Forestry Label, 2023)

Table 4. The nine criteria for the Agro Farm Forestry label (Agro Farm Forestry Label, 2023)

1. Install an agroforestry system	6. Handle water with care
2. Striving for soil improvement	7. You position yourself as an example Agroforestry farm
3. Strive to strengthen biodiversity	8. Collaborate with educational or research institutions
4. Seeking social or cultural benefits	9. Actively collaborate in the Agroforestry network
5. Carbon sequestration	

4. Branding

Branding has been defined as a process through which a company seeks to add value by distinguishing itself and its products from competitors in the market **with private or collective trademarks** (Lozej and Visković, 2022). For consumers, brands can offer benefits in terms of reducing search costs and assuring quality whilst also building the status and prestige of the consumer (Starr and Brodie, 2016). For some authors, branding can include certification (Macfadyen and Huntington, 2007), but for the purposes of this report we will focus on activities that have been used to promote agroforestry outside certification. Branding can be achieved by individual producers, groups of producers, advertising awards won by a product, and by retailers.

4.1 Individual products

One potential advantage of “branding” rather than certification is that it can avoid the costs and regulations associated with certification. Instead, the brand “becomes a sign system for itself” (Starr and Brodie, 2016). Escribano et al. (2020) argues that specific brands or labels for agroforestry systems can allow farmers to identify agroforestry systems and create new value chains through value enhancement. The Ellen McArthur Foundation (2021) in a scoping design project proposed “Silvo cheese” as a possible future product that would promote the benefits of bringing together cows and walnut trees in a silvopastoral system (Figure 16).

Figure 16. In a concept design exercise, the Ellen McArthur Foundation (2021) proposed a cheese brand that directly markets the advantages of agroforestry

4.2 Producer groups

It is also possible for groups of people practising agroforestry to work together. For example, Suisse Nuss is a co-operative created by four farmers in Switzerland who produce walnuts, dry and crack them, and then sell them directly to bakeries (Swiss Nuss, 2024). The co-operative indicates that they are committed to local production, value-creation by the nut producers, the local cultural landscape, biodiversity, and compliance with Bio Suisse certification. One advantage of working together is that the products can be marketed through a single website (Figure 17). The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe also supports a sustainability register of brands and networks (ITC Sustainability Gateway and ITC Market Analysis Tools, 2023).

Figure 17. The Swiss Nuss Co-operative Website includes an online shop (Swiss Nuss, 2024)

4.3 Awards from food competitions

Separate from certification and branding, it is also possible to promote agroforestry products by promoting the receipt of awards. For example, the Concours Général Agricole competition in France has recently started an “agroforestry” award in addition to other awards for other agricultural practices and products, which is awarded annually at the Paris Agricultural Fair (Concours Général Agricole, 2024) (Figure 18).

Figure 18. The Concours Général Agricole Awards for Agroforestry in France (Concours Général Agricole, 2024)

4.4 Retailer-related branding

Individual supermarkets and retailer often develop their own branding schemes, which often expand on an existing certification scheme (Table 5).

Table 5. Example retail branding schemes in the UK (Angus et al. 2023)

Scheme name	Managing organisation	Scheme coverage
Tesco Nurture	Tesco	Food quality and safety; sustainable farming; Environmental care; Occupational health Supplementary Schemes. Fruit and vegetable standards. Aligns with Red Tractor and GLOBALG.A.P IFA.
Field to Fork	Marks and Spencer	Covers food safety, quality, animal welfare and environmental protection. Operators must also have either Red Tractor, or GlobalG.A.P certification
Farm Forward	MacDonalds	Focuses on net zero, improving soil health and increasing biodiversity. Milk and beef producers must be Red Tractor certified.

One example of a supermarket-led agroforestry branding scheme in the UK was “Woodland Eggs”. In 2004, Sainsbury’s (a major supermarket chain in the UK) launched woodland eggs with one penny donated to the Woodland Trust for every 12 eggs sold. As part of the branding, the UK Woodland Trust added its logo to the woodland eggs sold by Sainsbury’s plc. During 2013, the Woodland Trust reported the sale of about 400 million woodland eggs through the grocery retailer Sainsbury’s in the UK, equivalent to about 3.4% of the UK market. To qualify as woodland eggs, the egg producer needed to ensure at least a 20% tree cover in the free range area with some trees within a 20 m distance of the shed (Burgess et al. 2014) (Figure 19). Although Sainsbury’s still sells woodland eggs, the integration of trees in free-range poultry systems is now also required for the RSPCA Assured certification scheme which focuses on animal welfare (RSPCA Assured 2024). Hence the system has expanded beyond a single supermarket.

Figure 19. Woodland planting around an egg production unit (BSI Group, 2024)

5. Conclusions

This interim report highlights a complicated landscape in terms of the certification and branding of agroforestry products. The first point that is clear from the study is that all certification and branding builds on established regulations instituted by governments such as the safety of food and fibre products. A second point is that the process of certification and branding depends in part on the concerns of consumers. If the primary concern of a consumer is price, then that will tend to be the principal determinant of a purchase. As identified in a recent report for the AGROMIX project (Grant Agreement N° 862993), few agroforestry products are competitive with other products on the basis of price alone (Burgess et al., 2024). Hence the rationale for a consumer buying an agroforestry product is likely to depend on attributes such as the positive impact of agroforestry on biodiversity, animal welfare, carbon sequestration, and rural economies.

Certification and branding are established ways in which consumers can obtain information on the location and means of production of a product and potentially quality (Table 6). The process of certification and branding can also offer benefits for producers and retailers in terms of price, improved client relationships, market opportunities, and product differentiation. However, certification does also entail costs, which can be significant, and these costs tend to fall on the producer.

Table 6. Summary of possible benefits for certification and branding for producers, stakeholders in the value chain such as retailers, and consumers (after Macfadyen and Huntington, 2007)

Expected benefit	Producer	Retailer	Consumer
Price increase	✓	✓	
Improved client relationship	✓ (with retailer)	✓ (with consumer)	
Improved management	✓ (for certification)	✓ (for certification)	✓ (for certification)
Improved quality	✓ (for branding)	✓ (for branding)	✓ (for branding)
Improved knowledge		✓	✓
Access to markets	✓		
Improved public image	✓	✓	
Product differentiation	✓	✓	

Certification systems typically include both an organisation that promotes the certification system and an independent organisation that audits compliance with the standards. This process can become complicated as there are trade-offs between costs, robustness, and uptake. A considerable number of certification schemes for agroforestry products relate to traceability, for example, high value dehesa meat products or specialist nut oil products from a specific region. In the context of climate change, it is noteworthy that certified “carbon-neutral” agricultural products which typically involve the use of trees on farms are also starting to appear. It can be argued that the presence of such products will increase, creating substantial opportunities for agroforestry. There are also selected certification schemes, often promoted by conservation charities, that are used to certify the biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, for example, high stem orchards in Switzerland.

The above certification systems encompass agroforestry because agroforestry supports a broader objective. In recent years, there have been attempts to develop bespoke agroforestry labels, most notably the Agro Farm Forestry label in the Netherlands. It is interesting that the Agro Farm Forestry label places a substantial emphasis on social engagement. Most such initiatives have been developed with external support and it is likely that external support will continue to be needed if they are to develop further.

Certification schemes have their place, but there can also be benefits to individual organisations from individual branding of agroforestry products, or from working in groups to promote agroforestry products, for example through the joint development and use of a website. Building on initiatives such as “best agroforestry product” categories in food awards can also be helpful. Individual processors and supermarkets may also support agroforestry through their own tree-related branding schemes.

A further output (Deliverable 3.7) will be produced in June 2026 comprising guidelines for farmers and actors wishing to design business plans building on new certification and branding approaches. This will build on the experiences of farmers and stakeholders from agroforestry value chains across the six DigitAF living labs and the blockchain work in Spain, and their feedback on the analysis completed in this report.

6. Acknowledgements

The DigitAF project (Grant Agreement N° 101059794) is co-funded by the European Commission, European Research Agency, within the Horizon Europe programme, Cluster 6: “Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment”. The views and opinions expressed in this report are purely those of the writers and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

7. References

- AHDB (Agricultural and Horticultural Development Board) (2023). Assurance Schemes. Accessed 22 May 2024. <https://ahdb.org.uk/assurance-schemes>.
- Agro Farm Forestry Label (2023). Agro Farm Forestry Label. <https://www.agrofarmforestry.eu/>
- Anders, S., Souza-Monteiro, D. and Rouviere, E. (2010). Competition and credibility of private third party certification in international food supply. *Journal of International Food and Agribusiness Marketing*. 22: 3-4; 328-341.
- Angus, A., Burgess, P., Deeks, L., Yang, M. (2023). UK Farm Assurance Schemes and Food Produced to Higher Environmental Production Standards. Project for DEFRA, May 2023. Cranfield, United Kingdom: Cranfield University.
- BSI (British Standards Institute) (2024). Morrisons 'Better For Our Planet' eggs – certified to the BSI Kitemark for Carbon Neutral Products. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0N7e3X84cZs>
- Burgess, P.J., Belot, V., Buachie, E., Cuartero de Frias, F., Nedved, K., Rodríguez Arquero, E. (2014). The Economics of Woodland Eggs in the UK. 2nd European Agroforestry Conference 04-06 June 2014 Cottbus – Germany, Book of Abstracts 67-70. (Eds Palma JHN, Chalmin A, Burgess P, Smith J, Strachan M, Ruiz Mirazo J, Rosati A), European Agroforestry Federation. ISBN: 978-972-97874-4-7.
- Burgess, P.J., Giannitsopoulos, M.L., Graves, A.R., Dumper-Pollard, R., Tidjani, F. (2024). Policy Paper with Guidelines for Successful Value Networks for Mixed Farming and Agroforestry. Deliverable 5.5. for AGROMIX project. 28 April 2024. Bedfordshire : Cranfield University. 47 pp.
- Campbell, H. (2005). The rise and rise of EUREPGAP: European (re)invention of colonial food relations? *International Journal of Sociology of Food and Agriculture* 13, 1-19.
- CBI (Centre for the Promotion of Imports from developing countries) (2022). Entering the United Kingdom market for fresh fruit and vegetables. <https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/fresh-fruit-vegetables/united-kingdom/market-entry>
- Chever, T., Gonçalves, A., Lepeule, C. (2022). Research for AGRI Committee – Farm certification schemes for sustainable agriculture, state of play and overview in the EU and in key global producing countries, concepts and methods, European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, Brussels.
- Concours Général Agricole (2024). Concours des Pratiques Agro-écologiques. <https://palmares.concours-general-agricole.fr/pratiques-agro-ecologiques>
- Defhesa (2021). Blockchain-based Certification Platform. <https://defhesa.org/plataforma-de-certificacion-basada-en-blockchain/>
- Defhesa (2023). Spanish Sustainable Beef Alliance. Sustainability and Quality [English translation] <https://defhesa.org/acerca-de/>
- EggInfo (2023). British Lion eggs. <https://www.egginfo.co.uk/british-lion-eggs>
- EIP-AGRI (2017). EIP-AGRI Focus Group on Agroforestry: Final report.
- EIP-AGRI (2024). Agroforestry network in Tuscany (NEWTON) https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/agroforestry-network-tuscany-newton_de
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2021). The Big Food Redesign: Regenerating Nature with the Circular Economy. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/2030-future-products-silvo>
- Escribano, M., Gaspar, P., Mesias, F.J. (2020). Creating market opportunities in rural areas through the development of a brand that conveys sustainable and environmental values. *Journal of Rural Studies*. 75, 206-215.
- European Commission (2002). Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32002R0178>
- European Commission (2024). Geographical indications and quality schemes explained https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/geographical-indications-and-quality-schemes/geographical-indications-and-quality-schemes-explained_en
- Fair to Nature (2023). The Fair to Nature Standard. Version 3.1a. June 2023 <https://fairtonature.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Fair-to-Nature-Standard-v3.1a-June-2023.pdf>

- FAO, WHO (1999). Guidelines for the Production, Processing, Labelling and Marketing of Organically Produced Foods. Rome: FAO. (available at www.fao.org/input/download/standards/360/cxg_032e.pdf)
- Forestry Service Group (2022) The Land+ system. <http://www.nvforest.com/FSG/Home.html>
- GLOBALG.A.P. (2023a). About Use. Accessed 22 May 2024. <https://www.globalgap.org/about/>
- GLOBALG.A.P. (2023b). Certification bodies. Accessed 23 May 2024. <https://www.globalgap.org/certification-bodies/>
- GLOBALG.A.P. (2023c). GLOBALG.A.P. secures a continuity option for the IFA livestock scope. <https://www.globalgap.org/news/globalgap-secures-a-continuity-option-for-the-ifa-livestock-scope/>
- Hochstamm Suisse (2018.) Hochstamm Suisse – The label for products from the Swiss Hochstamm orchard <https://www.hochstammsuisse.ch/produkte/>
- IAF (International Accreditation Forum) (2024). Accreditation Bodies. <https://iaf.nu/en/accreditation-bodies/>
- Iberchain Cartel (2022). Iberchain. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GNgzep3GeEQ>
- ITC Sustainability Gateway and ITC Market Analysis Tools (2023). ITC Sustainability Map. <https://sustainabilitymap.org/home>
- ISO (2012). ISO/IEC 17065:2012. Conformity assessment — Requirements for bodies certifying products, processes and services. <https://www.iso.org/standard/46568.html>
- Kopplin, C., Sänn, A. (2020). Begründung und Identifikation von Gütesiegeln in der Agroforstwirtschaft – Studien mithilfe von Conjointanalyse, Preisanalyse und Akzeptanzforschung [Justification and identification of quality seals in agroforestry - studies using co-analysis, price analysis and acceptance research]. Bayreuth University. 48 pp
- Label Haie (2024). A certification system for the preservation of hedges. <https://labelhaie.fr/qu-est-ce-que-le-label-haie/>
- Lozej, S.L., Visković, N.R. (2022). Branding, labelling and certification: Geographical and anthropological insights. Acta Geographica Slovenica, 62, 51–61.
- Macfadyen, G., Huntington, T. (2007). Potential Costs and Benefits of Fisheries Certification for Countries in the Asia-Pacific Region. Bangkok: Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/4/ai002e/ai002e00.pdf>
- Meuwissen, M.P.M., Velthuis, A.G.J., Hogeveen, H., Huirne, R.B.M. (2003). Traceability and certification in meat supply chains. Journal of Agribusiness, 21, 167–181.
- Morrisons (2024). Morrisons eggs achieve the first UK carbon neutral BSI Kitemark™ certification. <https://www.morrisons-corporate.com/media-centre/corporate-news/morrisons-eggs-achieve-the-first-uk-carbon-neutral-bsi-kitemark-certification/>
- Origin Food (2024). AOP Vaudoise walnut oil. <https://www.originfood.info/huile-noix-vaudoise-aop/>
- PEFC (2018). A leap forward for sustainable forest management and smallholders. <https://pefc.org/news/a-leap-forward-for-sustainable-forest-management-and-smallholders-1>
- PEFC (2023). Urban Green Standard and Agroforestry: after the pilot test, the last public consultation opens. <https://www.pefc.it/news/standard-verde-urbano-e-agroforestazione-dopo-il-test-pilota-si-apre-ultima-consultazione-pubblica-1>
- PEFC (2024). What is Certification? <https://www.pefc.org/what-we-do/our-approach/what-is-certification>
- RSPCA Assured (2024). Egg-Laying Hens. <https://www.rspcaassured.org.uk/farmed-animal-welfare/egg-laying-hens/#HensWelly>
- Sainsburys (2024). Respectful Medium Carbon Neutral Free Range Eggs x6. <https://www.sainsburys.co.uk/gol-ui/product/respectful-medium-carbon-neutral-free-range-eggs-x6>
- Starr, R.G., Brodie, R.J. (2016). Certification and authentication of brand value propositions. Journal of Brand Management 23, 716–731.
- SOSTVAN (2018). Sostenibilidad de las Vacas Nodrizas. <https://www.sostvan.com/>
- Swiss Nuss (2024). Swiss walnuts - We make it possible. <https://www.swissnuss.ch/>
- Swiss PDO-PGI Association (2024). Huile de Noix Vaudoise AOP. <https://www.aop-igp.ch/en/huile-de-noix-vaudoise-aop>
- Tranchina, M., Ripamonti, A., Cella, F., Mantino, A., Rolo, V., Prins, E., Thissen, W., den Herder, M., Hubner, R., Bohdan, L., Cumplido-Marin, L., Burgess, P.J. (2023). Schematic Maps of the Agroforestry Value Chain for each Living Lab. DigitAF Deliverable 3.1. 15 December 2023

- UK Government (2009). The Organic Products Regulations 2009. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2009/842/contents>
- UK Government (2020). Guidance Organic food: UK approved control bodies. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/organic-food-uk-approved-control-bodies>
- YouGov (2021). The UK'S Trust in Food Index. https://redtractor.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/HL_UKTIFI_landscape_pr13_final-1.pdf
- Woodland Trust (2020). Sainsbury's. <https://www.woodlandtrust.org.uk/partnerships/our-partners/sainsburys/>